

THE INFLUENCE OF THE METHOD OF PRODUCTION ON THE CONTENT OF MINERAL SUBSTANCES AND NITRATES IN LETTUCE

ALEKSANDRA GOVEDARICA-LUČIĆ, GORAN PERKOVIĆ, VASKOVIĆ
JELENA¹

SUMMARY: The lettuce is a very good and inexpensive source of minerals (N, P, K), but in the winter it is prone to accumulation of toxic substances (nitrates). The main goal of our research is to examine the impact of new technologies of production (land cover) on the quality of lettuce produced in the winter. Mineral content varied depending on the mode of production. The values of nitrogen content in lettuce tend to rise from bare ground (2.89-4.58%) to covered (3.09-4.85%) soil. The type of material that covers the land also has an impact on the content of potassium. The applied versions of the cover did not significantly affect the phosphorus content. There is a trend of nitrate increase when applying different methods of production.

Key words: salad, quality, cultural practices.

INTRODUCTION

Lettuce is a very valuable vegetable variety because of its dietetic characteristics, its vitamin values, the possibilities of production, and its presence on the markets during the whole year. It belongs to the sort of green and yellow vegetables that have a special significance in the diet because of a high content of scarce micronutrients such as copper, zinc, iron and magnesium, and especially in the period (spring-autumn) when there is a lack of these micronutrients (Miskovic et al., 2001; Lazic et al., 2001).

Biochemical content of the edible parts of the vegetables depends on the variety, and on the applied agricultural techniques (Lazic, et al., 2000). According to the research of the aforesaid authors, the aim of using new technologies in vegetable production is profitability along with a rational use of all the inputs directed towards the quality and environmental protection. There are also some significant results (Škorić M. 1996, Bošnjak Đ. 2005) indicating that the increased use of drop-by-drop irrigation system, along with covering of land with a suitable foil and use of nutritive elements, contribute to making a quality final product.

Original professional paper / *Originalni stručni rad*

¹Aleksandra Govedarica-Lučić, PhD, Assistant Professor; Goran Perković, PhD, Assistant Professor, Jelena Vasković, B.Sc. in Agriculture, Student II cycle (master degree), Faculty of Agriculture, University of East Sarajevo, Vuka Karadzica Street 30, 71123 East Sarajevo.
Corresponding author: Aleksandra Govedarica-Lučić, e-mail: sandraklepic@yahoo.com; phone: 0038757342701.

The quality of lettuce largely depends on the content of mineral substances (N; P; K), as well as on the content of nitrate, which in larger quantities can be harmful for human consumption. The basic aim of our researches is to test the influence of new production technologies (land covering) on the chemical composition of lettuce.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

During the two-year period (2009-2010), these tests were carried out on the lettuce varieties Archimedes RZ, Santoro RZ and Kibou RZ in a greenhouse without additional heating on the experimental field that belongs to the Faculty of Agriculture in East Sarajevo.

The trial was set in a randomized block system with four repetitions on the experimental plot sized 2.4m² (0.3x8m). There were three rows in this experimental plot, and each row represented a new variety. Planting of the substrate Klasmann for production of the planting material was done in containers, without nosedive in the first decade of September. The planting material, which was 25 days old, was planted at the distance of 20 cm within the row, and at the distance of 30 cm between the rows, so the complex of 150,000 plants/ha was achieved. As for the irrigation system, we used a drop-by-drop one, which was set together with the covering of land. We used four variants of land covering in the trial: mulching before planting with black polyethilen foil; agrotexile covering of plants after planting with agrotexile (17 grams); combination of mulching and agrotexile.

Picking of lettuce was done in the phase of its technological maturity. The chemical analysis of the planting material, i.e. the content of nitrogen, potassium, phosphorus and nitrates was done at the Chemical and Technology Faculty in Novi Sad by applying standard methods used by many scientific institutions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

While analyzing the two-year research results, it was determined that lettuce contained between 3.14 % - 4.8 % of nitrogen. The content of nitrogen in lettuce depended on the applied variants of covering. The average content in all the applied variants of covering was 3.14%.

The highest content of nitrogen (3.34%) was found when the agrotexile variant was applied, and the lowest one was found in the control variant (2.89%).

The differences in the content of nitrogen in the applied variants of covering, compared to the control one, were estimated at the threshold of significance of 1% (Tab. 1).

Depending on the selected varieties, the content of nitrogen differed within the range 2.84% - 3.50%. The determined differences in nitrogen content of the variety Archimedes (3.50%) compared to the varieties Santoro (2.84%) and Kibou (3.8%) were at the level of significance of $P < 0.01$.

Tab.1. The means of nitrogen content (%) in lettuce in 2009
 Tab.1 Srednje vrijednosti sadržaja azota (%) kod salate u 2009.godini

Covering land/pokrivanje zemljišta (A)	Variety /Sorta (B)			Average /Prosjek
	Archimed	Santoro	Kibou	
Control/kontrola	3.11	2.62	2.95	2.89
covering of black PE foil/pokrivanje sa crnom polietilenskom folijom	3.40	2.81	3.07	3.09
agrotexile/agrotekstil	3.87	3.07	3.23	3.34
black PE foil + agrotexile/crna polietil.folija + agrotekstil	3.62	2.84	3.14	3.23
Average/Prosjek	3.50	2.84	3.08	3.14
LSD	A	B	AxB	
0.05	0.04	0.03	0.07	
0.01	0.05	0.05	0.10	

The average content of nitrogen in the second year of researches was 4.68%. This content is by 1.54% higher than the one from the first year of the trial. The influence of different variants of covering on the content of nitrogen in the leaves of lettuce was prominent in the second year of the research, too. The control variant resulted in the lowest content of nitrogen (4.58%) while the polyeten foil variant resulted in the highest content of nitrogen (4.85%).

The varieties do not show more significant differences in the nitrogen content. The highest nitrogen content was determined in the Archimedes variety (4.90%), while the other two tested varieties had approximately the same nitrate content – Santoro (4.56%) and Kibou (4.60%).

By analyzing the interaction effect between the covering and the variety, it is interesting to conclude that the differences in the nitrogen content among the varieties tested on the fourth variant of covering were not statistically justified.

Tab.2. The means of nitrogen content (%) in lettuce in 2010
 Tab.2. Srednje vrijednosti sadržaja azota (%) kod salate u 2010.godini

Covering land/pokrivanje zemljišta (A)	Variety /Sorta (B)			Average /Prosjek
	Archimed	Santoro	Kibou	
Control/kontrola	4.96	4.33	4.44	4.58
covering of black PE foil/pokrivanje sa crnom polietilenskom folijom	5.16	4.72	4.69	4.85
agrotexile/agrotekstil	4.82	4.58	4.52	4.64
black PE foil + agrotexile/crna polietil.folija + agrotekstil	4.67	4.62	4.73	4.67
Average/Prosjek	4.90	4.56	4.60	4.68
LSD	A	B	AxB	
0.05	0.11	0.10	0.20	
0.01	0.15	0.13	0.27	

The phosphorus content.

Human nutritive needs for phosphorus range from 550 to 650 mg on a daily basis (Novaković et al. 2002). Phosphorus is important for all vital functions of our body. It is a component of bones, teeth, RNA and DNA, of phospholipids, every membrane of every cell, of the basic energy unit of ATP, and a certain number of enzymes and coenzymes.

The average phosphorus content in all the variants of covering applied regardless of the variety itself was 0.82%. The differences in phosphorus content among the variants of covering applied did not have statistical validation. The differences in the content of Phosphorus in the varieties Santoro and Kibou compared to the variety Archimedes, were estimated at the level of 1%

Tab.3. Means of phosphorus content (%) in lettuce in 2009.year
Tab.3. Srednje vrijednosti sadržaja fosfora (%) kod salate u 2009.godini

Covering land/ <i>pokrivanje zemljišta (A)</i>	Variety / <i>Sorta (B)</i>			Average / <i>Prosjek</i>
	Archimed	Santoro	Kibou	
Control/ <i>kontrola</i>	0.76	0.93	0.82	0.84
covering of black PE foil/ <i>pokrivanje sa crnom polietilenskom folijom</i>	0.79	0.77	0.90	0.82
agrotexile/ <i>agrotekstil</i>	0.74	0.88	0.89	0.84
black PE foil + agrotexile/ <i>crna polietil.folija + agrotekstil</i>	0.72	0.81	0.91	0.81
Average/ <i>Prosjek</i>	0.75	0.85	0.88	0.82
LSD	A	B	AxB	
0.05	0.04	0.03	0.07	
0.01	0.05	0.04	0.09	

The phosphorus content in the second year of research ranged from 1.33 to 1.59%. The average content of all the variants was 1.49%, which is by 1.11% more than in the previous year. The varieties tested had approximately the same phosphorus content in leaves. The only significant differences in phosphorus content were observed between varieties Santoro (1.53%) and Kibou (1.44).

The highest content of phosphorus (1.54%) was found in the combination of mulching + agrotexile, while the lowest content was found in the controls (1.43%).

Tab.4. the means of phosphorus content (%) in lettuce in 2010
 Tab.4. Srednje vrijednosti sadržaja fosfora (%) kod salate u 2010.godini

Covering land/ <i>pokrivanje zemljišta (A)</i>	Variety / <i>Sorta (B)</i>			Average / <i>Prosjek</i>
	Archimed	Santoro	Kibou	
Control/ <i>kontrola</i>	1.52	1.43	1.33	1.43
covering of black PE foil/ <i>pokrivanje sa crnom polietilenskom folijom</i>	1.56	1.57	1.44	1.52
agrotexile/ <i>agrotekstil</i>	1.47	1.53	1.50	1.50
black PE foil + agrotexile/ <i>crna polietil.folija + agrotekstil</i>	1.56	1.59	1.48	1.54
<i>Average/Prosjek</i>	1.52	1.53	1.44	1.49
LSD	A	B	AxB	
0.05	0.10	0.17	0.17	
0.01	0.13	0.11	0.23	

The potassium content.

The major physiological role of K is regulation in maintaining water balance in the human body. It is considered that the daily need for K is 0.8 to 1.3 g. According to Novakovic et al. (2002), people who frequently eat "fast food" and do not take fresh fruit and vegetables may have a low potassium intake.

The two-year research results showed that potassium content ranged from 3.81% to 4.81%, depending on the year, the variety and the covering.

Tab.5. The means of potassium content (%) in lettuce in 2009
 Tab.5. Srednje vrijednosti sadržaja kalijuma (%) kod salate u 2009.godini

Covering land/ <i>pokrivanje zemljišta (A)</i>	Variety / <i>Sorta (B)</i>			Average / <i>Prosjek</i>
	Archimed	Santoro	Kibou	
Control/ <i>kontrola</i>	4.46	3.88	4.15	4.16
covering of black PE foil/ <i>pokrivanje sa crnom polietilenskom folijom</i>	3.81	4.10	4.61	4.49
agrotexile/ <i>agrotekstil</i>	5.01	4.75	4.86	4.87
black PE foil + agrotexile/ <i>crna polietil.folija + agrotekstil</i>	4.73	4.54	4.65	4.64
<i>Average/Prosjek</i>	4.74	4.31	4.57	4.54
LSD	A	B	AxB	
0.05	0.06	0.05	0.11	
0.01	0.08	0.07	0.15	

The differences in the variants of covering are evaluated at the level of significance of $P < 0.01$, which indicates that the type of material used for covering of the soil affects the content of potassium in lettuce leaves. The gained results are in agreement with Balalić's reports (2004) which say the different methods of production (without mulching, mulching, mulching + agrotexile) show very significant differences in K content in lettuce.

The differences are also noticed in the potassium content and in different varieties. The highest content is recorded in the case of the variety Archimedes (4.74%). The variety Kibou had (4.57%), while the lowest content was recorded in the case of the variety Santoro (4.31%).

The differences among the varieties are highly significant, indicating that the varieties affect the potassium content in lettuce leaves. The results of the research confirmed that the potassium content depends on the variety (Koudela and Petrikova, 2008)

The highest content of potassium is found in all varieties in the case of the variant agrotexile Archimedes (5.01%), Santoro (4.75%), Kibou (4.86%).

The average content of potassium in the second year of research, regardless of the treatments tested, was 4.47%, which is similar to the previous research year.

Tab.6. Mean values of potassium content (%) in lettuce in 2010
Tab.6. Srednje vrijednosti sadržaja kalijuma (%) kod salate u 2010.godini

Covering land/ <i>pokrivanje zemljišta (A)</i>	Variety / <i>Sorta (B)</i>			Average / <i>Prosjek</i>
	Archimed	Santoro	Kibou	
Control/ <i>kontrola</i>	4.44	3.85	4.12	3.89
covering of black PE foil/ <i>pokrivanje sa crnom polietilenskom folijom</i>	4.74	4.10	4.58	4.45
agrotexile/ <i>agrotekstil</i>	5.01	4.74	4.86	4.87
black PE foil + agrotexile/ <i>crna polietil.folija + agrotekstil</i>	4.72	4.53	4.80	4.68
Average/ <i>Prosjek</i>	4.72	4.28	4.59	4.47
LSD	A	B	AxB	
0.05	0.10	0.17	0.17	
0.01	0.13	0.11	0.23	

The variants of covering applied affected the potassium content in the second year of research, too. The differences between the variants of covering were significant at the level of 1%. The values of potassium content ranged between 3.89% (control) and 4.87% (agrotexile). Balalic (2004), in his work, also reports about the results similar to ours.

In this year of research the differences in the content of potassium per variety were noticeable, too. The differences in potassium content between varieties Archimedes and Kibou were significant at the level of 1%, while the same differences between varieties Archimedes and Santoro i.e. Santoro and Kibou had significance at the level of 5%. The analysis of the interaction effect between a variety and a covering shows that it is highly significant in this year of research, too.

The nitrate content in lettuce depends on many factors. There is more nitrate in vegetables cultivated with higher doses of nitrogen and organic fertilizers at low relative air humidity, under drought conditions, low light intensity, during the short day, and temperatures above 25 °C degrees. According to the research by Kastori and Petrovic (2003), the interaction of temperature and light intensity is very significant for accumulation of nitrate. The cited authors point out that the accumulation of nitrate favors high substrate temperature and low light intensity.

The research results show that the four types of covering showed different nitrate contents. The highest content of nitrate (3192.25 mg/kg) was recorded in the application of agrotexile variant, and the lowest nitrate content (2597.83 mg / kg) in the control variant. The nitrate content ranged from 2606.12 mg / kg to 3464.56 mg/kg depending on the variety.

Tab.7. The mean values of nitrate (mg/kg) in lettuce in 2009
 Tab.7. Srednje vrijednosti sadržaja nitrata (mg/kg) u salati u 2009.godini

Covering land/ <i>pokriivanje zemljišta (A)</i>	Variety / <i>Sorta (B)</i>			Average /Prosjeak
	Archimed	Santoro	Kibou	
Control/ <i>kontrola</i>	3313.00	2290.00	2190.50	2597.83
covering of black PE foil/ <i>pokriivanje sa crnom polietilenskom folijom</i>	3491.50	2403.00	2523.00	2805.83
agrotexile/ <i>agrotekstil</i>	3652.50	3253.00	2681.00	3192.25
black PE foil + agrotexile/ <i>crna polietil.folija + agrotekstil</i>	3411.25	2782.25	3029.75	3074.41
Average/ <i>Prosjeak</i>	3464.56	2682.06	2606.12	2917.58
LSD				
0.05	97.04	84.03		168.08
0.01	129.70	112.3 2		224.66

In the second year of research, the average value of nitrate content ranged from 2197.25 mg/kg (control) to 2526.25 mg/kg (agrotexile).

The differences determined in the average values of nitrate content at different variants of covering are rated at the threshold of significance of 1%, only the differences stated between the third and fourth variant of covering were not statistically justified.

Tab.8. The mean values of nitrate (mg/kg) in lettuce in 2010
 Tab.8. Srednje vrijednosti sadržaja nitrata (mg/kg) u salati u 2010.godini

Covering land/pokrivanje zemljišta (A)	Variety /Sorta (B)			Average Prosjek
	Archimed	Santoro	Kibou	
Control/kontrola	2727.25	2001.50	1863.00	2197.25
covering of black PE foil/pokrivanje sa crnom polietilenskom folijom	2831.75	2211.00	2136.50	2393.08
agrotexile/agrotekstil	2889.70	2524.00	2165.00	2526.25
black PE foil + agrotexile/crna polietil.folija + agrotekstil	2923.00	2148.50	2487.00	2519.50
Average/Prosjek	2842.90	2221.25	2162.87	2409.02
LSD				
0.05	61.61	53.34		213.47
0.01	82.35	71.30		285.33

In the second year of research, the order of the varieties studied, in terms of this trait, was identical to the one in the previous year. Archimedes variety had the highest average value of nitrate content (2842.9 mg/kg), and Kibou variety had the lowest one (2162.87 mg/kg). The research by Ekonomakis and Saed (2002) showed that nitrate accumulation depends on the variety. Similar results are found in the works of Lazic et al. (2002). According to their research, the nitrate content is a varietal characteristics and leafy lettuce has the highest level (350.30 mg/kg fresh weight) and Roman salad the lowest of nitrate content (310, 90 mg/kg fresh mass).

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the two-year studies of the effect of production methods on the mineral substances and nitrate content in lettuce, the following conclusions can be made:

- The content of mineral substances varied depending on the way of production. The nitrogen content was significantly higher in the covered soil. The values of nitrogen content in lettuce tend to rise from bare ground (2.89-4,58%) to a covered (3,09-4,85%) soil. The type of material for covering soil also has an effect on the content of potassium. The highest potassium content of 4.87% was evident in the variant of covering soil with agrotexile, which is 18% more compared to the control variant.

- The covering variants applied did not significantly affect the phosphorus content.

- The nitrate content estimated as a harmful substance for human consumption depended on the method of production. There is an emphasized trend of increasing

nitrate with the application of various methods of production. The highest nitrate content (2526.25-3192.25 mg/kg) was in the variant of covering soil with agrotexile, which is 16% more compared to the control variant (2197.25-2597.83 mg/kg).

•The values of the maximum nitrate content in our trial were below the acceptable standard (4500 mg/kg for lettuce grown in the protected space) as provided by the European Commission EC.

REFERENCES

- BALALIĆ, I. Influence of method of production and substrates on yield and quality of lettuce (*Lactuca sativa* L.). Master's thesis. Faculty of Agriculture, Novi Sad, 2004.
- BOŠNJAK, Đ., GVOZDENOVIĆ, Đ., MILIĆ, S. Turnus as a base irrigation regime pepper. Proceedings of the Institute of Field and Vegetable Crops in Novi Sad ,41:113-143, 2005.
- EKONOMAKIS, C.D., SAID, M. Effect of solution temperature on growth and shoot nitrate content of lettuce grown in solution culture. Acta Hort. 579: II Balkan Symposium on Vegetables and Potatoes, Thessaloniki, Greece, 71, 2002.
- KASTORI, R., PETROVIĆ, N. Nitrates in vegetables. Physiological, ecological and agro-technical aspects. Novi Sad, 2003.
- KOUDELA, M., PETRIKOVA, K. Nutrients content and yield in selected cultivars of leaf lettuce (*Lactuca sativa* L. var. *crispa*). Hortscience, Prague, 35(3)99-106, 2008.
- LAZIĆ, B., ĐUROVKA, M., GVOZDENOVIĆ-VARGA, J. The influence of ecological conditions and agro technical practices on yield and quality of red onion. Proceedings of the Scientific Institute of trench and arable farming in Novi Sad, 33:135-144, 2000.
- LAZIĆ, B., MARKOVIĆ, V., ĐUROVKA, M., ILIN, Ž. Influence of biological factors and production on the quality of vegetables. Food and Nutrition, 43 (3-6)135-137, 2002.
- LAZIĆ, B., ĐUROVKA, M., LAZIĆ, S., MARKOVIĆ, V. The importance and possibility of the production of quality safe vegetables. Modern agriculture, 1-2(50)11-16, 2001.
- MISKOVIĆ, A., LAZIĆ, S., ZEREMSKI, T. Nutritive value of leafy vegetables, depending on the type and variety. I. International Symposium on "Food in the 21st Century" Proceedings, pp. 657-662, Subotica, 2001.
- NOVAKOVIĆ, B., MIROSAVLJEV, M., JEVTIĆ, M. Food Hygiene. Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad, 2002.

UTICAJ METODE PROIZVODNJE NA SADRŽAJ MINERALNIH MATERIJA I NITRATA U SALATI

ALEKSANDRA GOVEDARICA-LUČIĆ, GORAN PERKOVIĆ, JELENA
VASKOVIĆ

Izvod

Salata je jako dobar i jeftin izvor mineralnih materija (N, P, K) međutim u zimskom periodu sklona je i nakupljanju štetnih materija (nitrata). Osnovni cilj naših istraživanja je ispitati uticaj novih tehnologija proizvodnje (pokrivanje zemljišta) na kvalitet salate proizvedene u zimskim uslovima. Sadržaj mineralnih materija varirao je u zavisnosti od načina proizvodnje. Vrijednosti sadržaja azota imaju tendenciju porasta od nepokrivenog zemljišta (7.47%) ka pokrivenom (7.98%) zemljištu. Vrsta materijala za pokrivanje zemljišta također ima uticaja i na sadržaj kalijuma. Primjenjene varijante pokrivanja nisu značajno uticale na sadržaj fosfora. Izražena je tendencija povećanja nitrata sa primjenom različitih načina proizvodnje.

Ključne riječi: salata, kvalitet, agrotehničke mjere.

Received / *Primljen*: 25.08.2013.

Accepted / *Prihvaćen*: 21.10.2013.